

The Effect of Perceived Environmental Knowledge, Perceived Environmental Responsibilities, Environmental Concern, Subjective Norms, and Attitudes on Green Buying Behavior

Riski Yulika Dewi¹⁾, Kurnia Rina Ariani²⁾

1) Faculty of Economics and Business, Muhammadiyah University of Surakarta, Indonesia

2) Faculty of Economics and Business, Muhammadiyah University of Surakarta, Indonesia

Abstract: Awareness of environmental issues has started to grow in Indonesia, making this issue interesting to discuss. The younger generation of consumers are chosen because they are more concerned about and responsible for the environment, and like environmental protection issues. This study aims to analyze the factors that influence consumer green buying behavior among the younger generation in Solo Raya. This type of research is quantitative with primary data obtained through a questionnaire. Total sample 242 Respondents. The method used to determine the sample is purposive sampling technique. Data processing techniques use the SEM-PLS 3.0 application. The tests used are the Outer Model Test and Inner Model Test. The results showed that (1) Perceptions of perceived environmental responsibility, subjective norms, and attitudes have a positive and significant effect on green purchasing behavior. (2) Perceived environmental knowledge and environmental awareness do not have a significant effect but have a positive direction on green purchasing behavior. The results of this research will be useful for policy strategists and government organizations to create campaigns to encourage green buying behavior among young consumers.

Keywords: Perceived Environmental Knowledge, Perceived Environmental Responsibilities, Environmental Concern, Subjective Norms, Attitude, and Green Buying Behavior

I. INTRODUCTION

Economic progress and development are often associated with negative environmental consequences such as global warming, depletion of natural resources, acid rain, etc. Moreover, economic activities such as reckless industrial practices are responsible for global warming and degradation of natural resources. However, they also produce economic inequality in various sectors of society. Consumer indifference to the environmental, social and cultural impacts of growing consumerism has magnified the problem. Indonesia's relatively stable economic growth rate has also increased consumer purchasing power. Awareness of environmental issues is supported by consumer purchasing power, making Indonesia a potential market for environmentally friendly products. Green buying behavior involves purchasing environmentally friendly, recyclable or biodegradable goods, and avoiding products that harm the atmosphere and society. Green customer behavior is measured by the readiness or intention of customers to buy environmentally friendly goods. Some environmental experts claim that manufacturers will eventually turn to better resource and waste management due to customer demand, and scarcity of resources (Muldoon, 2004; Tseng & Bui, 2017). Therefore, actions also show consumers' mutual concern and responsibility for the environment which is increasingly evident. Young consumers are chosen because they care more about and are responsible for the environment, and like environmental protection issues (Connellet al., 1999; Martinsonet al., 1997). This makes them better understand the concept and importance of sustainable consumption, as well as its impact on the environment and society (Sliwka et al., 2006). Young consumers are also more receptive to new ideas (Ottmanet al., 2006). Thus, educated young consumers can become the driving force that brings about the desired changes in responsible consumption patterns. Furthermore, young consumers have a longer anticipated lifespan which can ensure that the changes introduced by them will last for a longer period of time, and be passed on to future generations.

II. LITERATUR REVIEW

1. Protection Motivation Theory

The Protective Motivation Theory (PMT) was introduced by Rogers in 1975 to establish the influence of fear factors on health habits and attitudes. In 1983, it was revised as a complete theoretical outline, including two main cognitive processes: hazard identification and coping assessment. The key elements of this model include perceived intensity, perceived risk, response effectiveness, and self-efficacy evaluation. Protective intention and protective behavior are two other model structures.

2. Theory of Planned Behavior

The theory of planned behavior (TPB) is unequalled in predicting human behavior, and this behavior is controllable compared to other psychological constructs. It is one of the most important social psychology theories for predicting people's behavior. In addition to using behavior and cultural expectations to predict purchase intentions, TPB also makes use of perceived behavioral control. This theory argues that the risk of people engaging in certain activities increases with positive attitudes toward the behavior, public acceptance of the behavior, and better control over the behavior (Ajzen, 1991).

3. Green Buying Behavior Theory

The behavior of purchasing green products is one of the pro-environmental behaviors referring to the purchase and consumption of products that have little impact on the environment (Mustofa, 2007). The buying behavior of green products leads to the preference and use of products that are environmentally friendly and/or produced using ecological processes and materials (Kilbourne and Pickett, 2008). According to Ottman (2006) the benefits of buying green products include efficiency and cost-effectiveness, health and safety, performance, symbolism and status, and convenience (Junaedi and Fatmawati, 2016).

4. Environmental Knowledge Theory

One form of environmental awareness is environmental knowledge. According to Fryxell and Lo (2003), knowledge of the environment can be defined as a general knowledge of facts, concepts and relationships between the natural environment and the surrounding ecosystems. Meanwhile, Koellner and Tovar (2009) define environmental knowledge as a set of ecological knowledge that an individual has from environmental topics (StiaRini, PutuGdeSukaatmadja, and GstAyuKtGiantari 2017).

5. Environmental Responsibility Theory

The theory underlying the emergence of the perception of environmental responsibility is NAM (Norm Activation Theory). Norm activation theory was developed to explain pro-social behavior related to pro-environmental behavior. This norm activation theory assumes that personal norms have a direct effect on behavior. Someone who buys organic products for functional purposes or health reasons will not be influenced by morals. The activation factor in the NAT model is influenced by perceptions of ecological problems, awareness of consequences and perceptions of behavioral control. The unity between awareness, responsibility, and personal norms influences individual intentions and behavior in pro-environment (Eriksson, and Nordlund, 2006).

6. Environmental Concern Theory

Angelovska et al. (2012), stated that environmental awareness is a possible predictor of purchasing behavior for environmentally friendly products. Concern for the environment can be considered as a commitment and emotional level of consumers towards various issues in the surrounding environment.

7. Subjective Norm Theory

Subjective norms (subjective norms) are one's perceptions or views of other people's beliefs that will affect interest in doing or not doing the behavior being considered Septifani (2014). According to Huda (2012) subjective norms are one's perceptions or assumptions about other people's expectations, certain behaviors that someone will or will not do. Because this perception is very subjective in nature, this dimension is referred to as a subjective norm.

8. Attitude Theory

Attitude is an expression of someone's likes or dislikes that can be reflected in a particular object. Attitude is the result of a person's psychological process, so this cannot be seen or observed directly but must be inferred from everything he does or says (Suprapti, 2010: 135). Attitude is a tendency that can be learned in every behavior with actions that mean pleasant or unpleasant towards the object (Schiffman and Leslie, 2008).

The Effect of Perceived Environmental Knowledge on Green Buying Behavior in the Young Generation in Solo Raya.

A higher level of ecological knowledge is required to take appropriate action towards environmental protection. Consumers with higher environmental knowledge tend to exhibit environmentally responsible behavior (Mostafa, 2006; Suki, 2013). Several studies have specifically found that consumer environmental knowledge positively influences green buying behavior (Mostafa, 2006; Young et al., 2010).

H1. Perceptions of consumer knowledge about environmental issues will influence the green buying behavior of the younger generation in Solo Raya.

The Effect of Perceived Environmental Responsibilities on Green Buying Behavior in the Young Generation in Solo Raya.

In a study conducted by (Lee, 2009) in Hong Kong, environmental responsibility was shown to significantly influence the green purchasing activities of youth. In terms of gender, unlike men, women have a higher tendency to continue to take a role in solving environmental problems. Therefore, the notion of perceived environmental responsibility requires further investigation to better understand its role as a predictor of green behavior and more precisely environmental activism.

H2. The perceived environmental responsibility will influence the green buying behavior of the younger generation in Solo Raya.

The Effect of Environmental Concern on Green Buying Behavior on Young Generation in Solo Raya.

Studies (Irawan and Darmayanti, 2012) show that Indonesian students' green consumer behavior is strongly influenced by environmental issues, whereas (Albayrak et al. 2013) found in their research in Turkey that environmental awareness is a strong predictor of behavioral intention. Thus, the higher the level of environmental awareness, the stronger the consumer's green purchasing intentions and behavior.

H3. The perceived environmental concern will influence the green buying behavior of the younger generation in Solo Raya.

The Effect of Subjective Norms on Green Buying Behavior in the Young Generation in Solo Raya

Istiana's research (2010) also states the same thing that subjective norms have a positive and significant effect on consumer purchase intentions. Subjective norms have also been shown to directly influence consumer behavior towards green procurement. Several previous studies reported that social pressure pushed customers to buy environmentally friendly goods (Ekawati 2020).

H4. Perceptions of subjective norms will influence the green buying behavior of the younger generation in Solo Raya.

The Effect of Attitude on Green Buying Behavior on the Young Generation in Solo Raya

Various studies examining the relationship between consumer ecological attitudes and green buying behavior have reported somewhat mixed results; while most studies find a positive relationship (Kozar and Connell, 2013; Mostafa, 2006; Tanner and WölflingKast, 2003) between the two. In addition, several experiments have also established a positive relationship between customer attitudes and purchase intentions.

H5. Perceived attitudes will influence the green buying behavior of the younger generation in Solo Raya

III. METHOD

This type of research uses quantitative research. Quantitative research is research from a data obtained in the form of numbers that can be obtained from calculating questionnaires and in the form of data. This study obtained primary data through a questionnaire-based survey. The target respondents are young people, especially the younger generation in Solo Raya with an age range of 18 to 30 years. The number of respondents involved in this survey was 242 people. The sample in this study was determined using the non-probability sampling method, namely a sampling technique that does not provide equal opportunities or opportunities for each member of the population to become a sample, using purposive sampling technique. This research was conducted using a Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach based on Partial Least Square (PLS). PLS is a component- or variant-based structural equation model (SEM). PLS-SEM analysis consists of two, namely the Outer model and Inner model Ghozali&Latan (2015).

IV. RESULTS

1. Characteristics of Respondents

The characteristics of the respondents are useful for knowing the overall picture of the research respondents. To find out the characteristics of the respondents can be seen in Table 1 below:

No.	Criteria	Information	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender	Man	138	57%
		Woman	104	43%
2	Age	18 - 20 years	165	68,2%
		21 - 23 years	56	23,1%
		24 - 26 years	8	3,3%
		27 - 29 years	5	2,1%
		30 years	8	3,3%
3	District/city origin address	Sragen	106	43,8%
		Kota Surakarta	55	22,7%
		Karanganyar	36	14,9%
		Klaten	15	6,2%
		Sukoharjo	12	5%
		Boyolali	10	4,1%
4	Work	Wonogiri	8	3,3%
		Student / Student	190	78,5%
		Private employees	12	5%
		Self-employed	11	4,5%
		civil servant	7	2,9%
		IRT	3	1,2%
5	Income	Other	19	7,9%
		<Rp. 500,000	143	59,1%
		Rp. 500,000 to Rp. 2,000,000	58	24%
		>Rp. 2,000,000	14	16,9%

Table 1. Characteristics of Respondents

From the table above it can be concluded that the majority of young generation respondents in Solo Raya at the time this research was conducted were male respondents, aged over 18 to 20 years, came from Sragen district, student work. and have a monthly income of less than Rp. 500,000 .

2. Measurement Model Test (Outer Model)

This model is used to test convergent validity, discriminant validity and the reliability of research instruments. To obtain accurate calculation results, validity and reliability testing in this study used smartPLS 3.0 software. The following is a model for the outer model test.

Picture 1. Outer Model Test

Based on picture 1. it is known that all indicators in this study have a factor loading value of > 0.5. This shows that all indicators in this study meet the convergent validity test. The outer model test that needs to be done next is the discriminant validity test. The results of the outer loading test for the discriminant validity of each indicator are presented in Table 3 below:

Variabel	Indicator	Convergent Validity Factor Loading Value	Information
Perceived Environmental Knowledge (X1)	X1.2	0.770	Valid
	X1.3	0.793	Valid
	X1.4	0.808	Valid
Perceived Environmental Responsibilities (X2)	X2.1	0.807	Valid
	X2.2	0.811	Valid
	X2.3	0.773	Valid
Environmental Concern (X3)	X3.1	0.747	Valid
	X3.3	0.810	Valid
	X3.4	0.603	Valid
	X3.5	0.736	Valid
Subjective Norms (X4)	X4.1	0.776	Valid
	X4.2	0.841	Valid
	X4.3	0.793	Valid
	X4.4	0.855	Valid
	X4.5	0.796	Valid
Attitude (X5)	X5.1	0.855	Valid
	X5.2	0.897	Valid
	X5.3	0.909	Valid
Green Buying Behavior (Y)	Y.1	0.791	Valid
	Y.2	0.719	Valid
	Y.3	0.831	Valid
	Y.4	0.790	Valid
	Y.5	0.798	Valid

Table 2. Outer Loading Test

Based on the table above, it is known that many research variable indicators have outer loading values > 0.7. However, according to (Chin, 1998) the measurement scale of the loading value of 0.5 to 0.6 is considered sufficient to meet the requirements of convergent validity. The data above shows that there are no variable indicators whose outer loading value is below 0.5, so that all indicators are declared feasible or valid for research use and can be used for further analysis.

Apart from looking at the outer loading value, convergent validity can also be assessed by looking at the AVE (Average Variance Extracted) value > 0.5 so that it can be said that convergent validity is valid (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). The following is the AVE value of each of the research variables:

Discriminant Validity

The discriminant validity test uses the cross loading value. An indicator is declared to meet discriminant validity if the indicator's cross loading value on a variable is the largest compared to other variables (Chin, 1998). The following is the cross loading value of each indicator:

Indicator	Perceived Environmental Knowledge (X1)	Perceived Environmental Responsibility (X2)	Environmental Concern (X3)	Subjective Norms (X4)	Attitude (X5)	Green Buying Behavior (Y)
X1.2	0.770	0.489	0.462	0.541	0.375	0.473
X1.3	0.793	0.568	0.496	0.514	0.331	0.521
X1.4	0.808	0.505	0.521	0.539	0.439	0.580
X2.1	0.485	0.807	0.502	0.465	0.539	0.520
X2.2	0.499	0.811	0.596	0.48	0.607	0.556
X2.3	0.579	0.773	0.514	0.612	0.346	0.614
X3.1	0.492	0.463	0.747	0.53	0.433	0.519
X3.3	0.530	0.558	0.810	0.542	0.482	0.541
X3.4	0.325	0.389	0.603	0.257	0.465	0.317
X3.5	0.438	0.545	0.736	0.398	0.534	0.45
X4.1	0.614	0.601	0.514	0.776	0.411	0.643
X4.2	0.599	0.602	0.526	0.841	0.428	0.634
X4.3	0.481	0.465	0.413	0.793	0.288	0.642
X4.4	0.561	0.552	0.551	0.855	0.361	0.695
X4.5	0.466	0.445	0.493	0.796	0.300	0.601
X5.1	0.421	0.515	0.56	0.345	0.855	0.421
X5.2	0.418	0.506	0.588	0.399	0.897	0.47
X5.3	0.452	0.612	0.577	0.422	0.909	0.529
Y.1	0.588	0.515	0.464	0.63	0.413	0.791
Y.2	0.473	0.528	0.489	0.572	0.398	0.719
Y.3	0.476	0.58	0.513	0.615	0.476	0.831
Y.4	0.55	0.56	0.524	0.667	0.355	0.790
Y.5	0.533	0.61	0.529	0.628	0.469	0.798

Table 3. Cross Loading

Based on the data presented in the table above, it can be seen that each indicator on the research variable has the largest cross loading value on the variable it forms compared to the cross loading value on other variables. Based on the results

obtained, it can be stated that the indicators used in this study have good discriminant validity in compiling their respective variables.

Reliability Test

The reliability test shows the level of consistency and stability of measuring instruments or research instruments in measuring a concept or construct (Abdillah and Hartono, 2015). Reliability testing in this study used Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha.

Composite Reliability is used to measure the reliability of a construct. The construct is declared reliable if the composite reliability has a value > 0.7, then the construct is declared reliable. The SmartPLS output results for composite reliability values can be shown in the table:

Variabel	Composite Reliability	Information
Environmental Concern (X3)	0.817	Reliable
Subjective Norms (X4)	0.907	Reliable
Perceived Environmental Knowledge (X1)	0.833	Reliable
Green Buying Behavior (Y)	0.890	Reliable
Attitude (X5)	0.917	Reliable
Perceived Environmental Responsibilities (X2)	0.840	Reliable

Table 4. Composite Reliability

Based on the table above, each variable has composite reliability > 0.7 with a variable value of environmental concern of 0.817, the subjective norm variable value is 0.907, the perceived environmental knowledge variable is 0.833, the green buying behavior variable is 0.890, the attitude variable is 0.917, and the environmental responsibility variable is perceived is 0.840. This shows that each variable used in this study can be said to be reliable.

The last reliability test is Cronbach's α (alpha) where this test is a statistical technique used to measure internal consistency in instrument reliability tests or psychometric data. According to Cronbach (1951), a construct is said to be reliable if the Cronbach alpha value is more than 0.60. Below are the results of the Cronbach alpha values which will be displayed in the following table:

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Information
Environmental Concern (X3)	0.706	Reliable
Subjective Norms (X4)	0.871	Reliable
Perceived Environmental Knowledge (X1)	0.702	Reliable
Green Buying Behavior (Y)	0.845	Reliable
Attitude (X5)	0.865	Reliable
Perceived Environmental Responsibilities (X2)	0.714	Reliable

Table 5. Cronbach's Alpha

Based on the table, it shows that all Cronbach alpha results have a value above 0.60, which means that the Cronbach alpha value meets the requirements so that all constructs can be said to be reliable.

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test can be seen from the tolerance value and variance inflation factor (VIF). Multicollinearity can be detected by a cut off value indicating a tolerance value > 0.1 or equal to a VIF value < 5. Below are the VIF values in this study:

Variabel	Environmental Concern (X3)	Subjective Norms (X4)	Perceived Environmental Knowledge (X1)	Green Buying Behavior (Y)	Attitude (X5)	Perceived Environmental Responsibilities (X2)
Environmental Concern (X3)				2.514		
Subjective Norms (X4)				2.240		
Perceived Environmental Knowledge (X1)				2.259		
Green Buying Behavior (Y)						
Attitude (X5)				1.930		
Perceived Environmental Responsibilities (X2)				2.635		

Table 6. Collenarity Statistic (VIF)

From the table above, the results of Collinierity Statistics (VIF) to see the multicollinearity test with the results of the environmental concern variable for green buying behavior are 2.514, for the value of the subjective norm variable for green buying behavior is 2.240, the value of the perceived environmental knowledge variable on green buying behavior is 2.259, the value of the attitude variable towards green buying behavior is 1.930, and the value of the perceived environmental responsibility variable is 2.635. Each variable has a cut-off value > 0.1 or equal to a VIF value < 5, so this does not violate the multicollinearity test.

3. Inner Model Analysis

Model Goodness Test (Goodness of Fit)

Structural model evaluation is carried out to show the relationship between the manifest and latent variables of the main predictor variables, mediators and outcomes in a complex model. The goodness-of-fit test of this model consists of two tests, namely R-Square (R^2) and Q-Square (Q^2). The value of R^2 or R-Square indicates the determination of the exogenous variables on the endogenous variables. The greater the value of R^2 , the better the level of determination. R^2 values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 can be concluded that the model is strong, moderate, and weak (Imam Ghozali, 2015). The value of the coefficient of determination can be shown in the following table:

Variabel	R Square Adjusted	Information
Green Buying Behavior (Y)	0.704	Strong

Table 7. Adjusted R Square Value

Based on the table above, R square is used to see the magnitude of the influence of perceived environmental knowledge, perceived environmental responsibility, environmental concern, subjective norms, and attitudes towards the green buying behavior variable with a value of 0.704 so it can be stated to have a strong value.

The next test is the Q-Square test. The value of Q^2 in testing the structural model is done by looking at the value of Q^2 (Predictive relevance). The Q^2 value can be used to measure how well the observed values produced by the model are also the parameters. The value of $Q^2 > 0$ indicates that the model has predictive relevance, while the value of $Q^2 < 0$ indicates that the model lacks predictive relevance.

Variabel	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)	Information
Environmental Concern (X3)	968.000	968.000		
Subjective Norms (X4)	1.210.000	1.210.000		
Perceived Environmental Knowledge (X1)	726.000	726.000		
Green Buying Behavior (Y)	1.210.000	688.911	0.431	Good
Attitude (X5)	726.000	726.000		
Perceived Environmental Responsibilities (X2)	726.000	726.000		

Table 8. Q-Square value

Based on the calculation results above, a Q-Square value of 0.431 is obtained. This value explains that the diversity of the research data can be explained by the research model of 43.1% while the remaining 56.9% is explained by other factors that are outside this research model. Thus the value of $Q^2 > 0$ indicates that the model has good goodness of fit.

Hypothesis testing

Testing the hypothesis in this study can be seen in the path coefficient value for direct influence. Test the path coefficient by using the bootstrapping process to see the t statistics or p values (critical ratio) and the original sample values obtained from the process.

The p value < 0.05 indicates that there is a direct or indirect effect, while the p value > 0.05 indicates that there is no direct or indirect effect. In this study, the significance value used was the t-statistic of 1.96 (significant level = 5% and 10%). The value of testing the hypothesis of this study can be shown in the following table:

Variabel	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Information
Perceived Environmental Knowledge (X1) -> Green Buying Behavior (Y)	0.107	0.109	0.068	1.570	0.117	No significant effect
Perceived Environmental Responsibility (X2) -> Green Buying Behavior (Y)	0.211	0.207	0.071	2.973	0.002**	Significantly influential
Environmental Concern (X3) -> Green Buying Behavior (Y)	0.063	0.066	0.059	1.066	0.287	No significant effect
Subjective Norm (X4) -> Green Buying Behavior (Y)	0.503	0.503	0.069	7.328	0.000**	Significantly influential
Attitude (X5) -> Green Buying Behavior (Y)	0.093	0.091	0.054	1.724	0.093*	Significantly influential

Table 9. Path Coefficient Value (Direct Effect)

P Values* : 10% significance

P Values** : 5% significance

Based on the results of the path coefficient above, it can be interpreted as follows:

The first hypothesis tests the perception of environmental knowledge that is felt to influence green buying behavior. The test results show that the t-statistic value is 1.570 and the original sample is positively charged with a p-value of 0.117. From these results, the t-statistic < 1.96 and p-value > 0.05 was obtained. So it can be concluded that hypothesis one is rejected where there is no significant effect between perceived environmental knowledge on green buying behavior. The results of this study are not in line with research conducted by (Yatish Joshi and Zillur Rahman, 2015) because in this study the respondents lacked substantial understanding and knowledge about the seriousness of environmental problems which could not motivate consumers to buy environmentally friendly. So it can be concluded that this study does not support previous research.

The second hypothesis is that perceived environmental responsibility will influence green buying behavior. The test results show that the t-statistic value is 2.973 and the original sample is positively charged with a p-value of 0.002. From these results, the t-statistic was > 1.96 and the p-value < 0.05 . So it can be concluded that the second hypothesis is accepted where there is a positive and significant influence between perceived environmental responsibility on green purchasing behavior. The results of this study are not in line with research conducted by (Guang-Wen Zheng, et al., 2020) where in this study environmental responsibility has a significant effect on green buying behavior because it is caused by the success of respondents to fulfill the need to protect the environment, and they do not reluctant to admit their responsibility in this case protecting the environment. So it can be concluded that this study does not support previous research.

The third hypothesis tests the perception that environmental awareness will influence green purchasing behavior. The test results show that the t-statistic value is 1.066 and the original sample is positively charged with a p-value of 0.287. From these results, the t-statistic < 1.96 and p-value > 0.05 was obtained. So it can be concluded that the third hypothesis is rejected where there is no significant influence between environmental awareness on green buying behavior. This research is in contrast to research conducted by (Guang-Wen Zheng, et al., 2020) where the results of this study on the environmental concern variable do not have a significant effect but have a positive direction towards green buying behavior. Empirical findings find that environmental issues have a major influence on consumer behavior towards the consumption of environmentally friendly goods. However, this research does not illustrate that the greater the concern for environmental sustainability, the more likely customers will deliberately buy environmentally friendly goods. So it can be concluded that this study does not support previous research.

The fourth hypothesis tests the perception of subjective norms that will influence green buying behavior. The test results show that the t-statistic value is 7,328 and the p-value is 0,000. From these results, the t-statistic was > 1.96 and the p-value < 0.05 . So it can be concluded that the hypothesis can be accepted where there is a positive and significant influence between subjective norms on green buying behavior. The results of this study are also in line with research conducted by Lee (2009) which states that the influence of subjective norms is the main predictor of purchasing decisions where the influence of subjective norms is able to suggest and strengthen an action or consumer buying behavior. So it can be concluded that this study supports previous research.

The fifth hypothesis tests the perception that attitudes will influence green buying behavior, using a significance level of 10%. The test results show that the t-statistic value is 1.724 and the original sample is positively charged with a p-value of 0.093. From these results, the t-statistic < 1.65 and p-value > 0.05 was obtained. So it can be concluded that the fifth hypothesis is accepted where there is a significant influence between attitudes towards green buying behavior with a significance of 10%. This research is also in line with research conducted by (Guang-Wen Zheng, et al., 2020) where the results of the research conducted are that attitudes have a positive and significant influence on green buying behavior where the results can be highlighted by the fact that a person's cognitive and logical assessment of the value of sustainable consumption activities is part of their attitude towards sustainable consumption. So it can be concluded that this study supports previous research.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion that has been carried out using the Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis method, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Perceived environmental knowledge has a positive and insignificant effect on green purchasing behavior, so the first hypothesis is not supported.
2. Perceived environmental responsibility has a positive and significant influence on green purchasing behavior, so the second hypothesis is supported.
3. Concern for the environment has a positive and insignificant influence on green purchasing behavior, so the third hypothesis is not supported.
4. Subjective norms have a positive and significant influence on green purchasing behavior, so the fourth hypothesis is supported.
5. Attitude has a positive and significant influence on green purchasing behavior, so that the fifth hypothesis is supported.

Research Limitations

The data collected is the result of the answers to the questionnaire through the google form of each respondent without going through direct interviews so as to allow the data to be less sharp in identifying respondents to the questionnaire statements submitted. Furthermore, the questionnaire in this study is closed so that each respondent will only answer the answer criteria that have been provided. This can allow each respondent to answer the questionnaire not in accordance with the actual situation.

Suggestion

It is hoped that further research can use other variables that have not been disclosed in this study in order to explain other factors that can also influence green purchasing behavior. Future research is expected to develop research through interviews or direct observation. Further research should be carried out with a larger number of respondents with varying characteristics in order to increase the generalization and diversity of the research results.

REFERENCES

- [1] Amit Kumar, Gupta. 2021. "Framing a Model for Green Buying Behavior of Indian Consumers: From the Lenses of the Theory of Planned Behavior." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 295: 126487. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.126487>.
- [2] Ayu, Ida et al. 2019. "Jurnal Internasional Multikultural Dan Pemahaman Multireligius Pengaruh Pengetahuan Lingkungan Terhadap Niat Beli Hijau Peran." : 627-35.
- [3] Ekawati, Trestina. 2020. "Kajian Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Niat Beli Produk Organik." *Journal of Business and Information Systems (e-ISSN: 2685-2543)* 2(1): 32-45.
- [4] Issn, P. 2022. "Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis , Vol . 11 No . 1 Juli 2022 E - ISSN : 2654-5837 , Hal 5 42 - 550." 11(1): 323-30.
- [5] Junaedi, Dita Kameilinda, and Indah Fatmawati. 2016. "Anteseden Pembelian Produk Hijau." *Jurnal Manajemen Pemasaran dan Jasa* 9(1): 175-86.
- [6] Manajemen, Studi, and Universitas Muhammadiyah. 2022. "Pengaruh Persepsian Tanggung Jawab Lingkungan Terhadap Perilaku Pembelian Produk Hijau Yang Dimediasi Oleh Norma Subjektif Dan Sikap Ravita Dwi Kusumawardani _ 1 a , Rini Kuswati _ 2 b *." (2020): 1-17.
- [7] Mokhtari, Samah, Mebarek Djebabra, Djamel Bellaala, and Wafa Boulagouas. 2017. "Manajemen Kualitas Lingkungan : Jurnal Internasional."
- [8] Morais. 2005. "Perilaku Konsumen." (April): 104.
- [9] Sia, Surendra Kumar, and Alphonsa Jose. 2019. "Attitude and Subjective Norm as Personal Moral Obligation Mediated Predictors of Intention to Build Eco-Friendly House." *Management of Environmental Quality: An International Journal* 30(4): 678-94.
- [10] Stia Rini, Ayu, I Putu Gde Sukaatmadja, and I Gst Ayu Kt Giantari. 2017. "Pengaruh Pengetahuan Lingkungan Dan Kepedulian Lingkungan Terhadap Sikap Dan Niat Beli Produk Hijau 'the Body Shop' Di Kota Denpasar." *Bisnis Universitas Udayana* 6(1): 137-66.
- [11] Unud, E-jurnal Manajemen. 2018. "Dan Keputusan Pembelian Fakultas Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Universitas Udayana (Unud), Bali , Indonesia Sifat Manusia Yang Tidak Pernah Puas Dan Mempunyai Beragam Keinginan Menuntut Produsen Untuk Selalu Membuat Produk Yang Bisa Memuaskan Konsumennya . Keingin." 7(3): 1452-80.
- [12] Yue, Beibei, Guanghua Sheng, Shengxiang She, and Jiaqi Xu. 2020. "Impact of Consumer Environmental Responsibility on Green Consumption Behavior in China: The Role of Environmental Concern and Price Sensitivity." *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 12(5): 1-16.
- [13] Zheng, Guang Wen et al. 2021. "Perceived Environmental Responsibilities and Green Buying Behavior: The Mediating Effect of Attitude." *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 13(1): 1-27.
- [14] SuprptaYasa, B., &Ekawati, N. (2015). *Peran Gender Dalam Menjelaskan Pengaruh Sikap Dan Norma Subyektif Terhadap Niat Beli*. E-Jurnal Manajemen Universitas Udayana, 4(6), 253648.